

Participatory tools

FOCUS GROUP

CLARIFY THE BIG IDEA TOGETHER: MEETING THE USER'S NEEDS

How will you ensure the project meets the need of the targeted user?

According to the OECD's (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) Oslo Manual (2005), an innovation is a novelty that finds its audience: "The implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service) or process, a new marketing method or a new organizational method in business practices, work organization or external relations".

Thus, by definition, innovation connects to users' needs and will be adopted by a wide range of practitioners. The basic assumption is that users are the ones who know their needs and expectations best. Even if the initial idea does not necessarily come from them, it is essential to verify the alignment/appropriateness between the intended outcomes of the project and the needs of the users.

How to solve it

It helps to check very early on that the users are on board. To do this, ideally, you need to involve them during the set-up of the project or consult them in parallel. They can also be

involved throughout the project to be consulted, make adjustments, and start developing it (see "Create Useful content").

A participatory method such as "Focus Group" is ideal because it helps to collect the participants' opinions and needs.

Word of advice

Before contacting users, the idea needs to be explored, the context(s) known (see "How to define the idea"). But of course, the manager must keep the possibility to adapt it after meeting the end-users.

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Focus Group - Confronting points of view on a given subject.

Description of the tool

- **What:** group interview, compare and share different ideas; to generate a rich understanding of participant's experiences and beliefs
- **How long:** 1h30 to 3h
- **How many:** 5 to 12

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

- **What you'll need:** sticky notes, flip chart, markers

Steps:

- A moderator guides the interview while a small group discusses the topics that the interviewer raises. The facilitator begins by proposing the group's operating rules and having them validated collectively (listening, benevolence, respect, etc.). This method unfolds open questions like a funnel. The first question is broad on the theme that the facilitator wishes to address, for example, "for you, what does animal welfare mean?" The next question explores the experience and practices of participants concerning the topic in more depth. The following questions are more specific and may, for example, ask for an opinion on a tool or gather particular needs.
- The facilitator should encourage participants to express themselves without any judgement. The objective is to gather all opinions. The facilitator can use different participatory tools in the different sessions.
- It is advisable to record the activity to illustrate the report with quotes.

Tips:

Invite the participants:

- Take care when creating the sample group(s): which people according to the objective?
- Ensure that participants can speak freely among themselves and that

there are no conflicts of interest within the group.

- Recruitment managed by partners directly involved with the target audience -> trust, easier to come, to feel engaged if you know the person who is asking you
- Create a clear invitation
- Secure participation on the day: be sure that enough participants are coming, make follow-up calls a few days before, and send a gentle reminder the day before

Prepare the content:

- Rigorous preparation:
 - Very well defined objectives
 - Method, precise sequence of events
- During the Focus Group:
 - Time is working against the group. Identify one person appointed to watch the time
 - Let each participant have the chance to express themselves. An experienced facilitator can help you

Logistic:

- No more than 10/12 people
- Minimum of 2 facilitators: one leading and the other taking notes

